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From Rabbit Pairs to ϕ

Many students perceive mathematics as dull and boring, describing it as too abstract and difficult to comprehend. For that reason, the true beauty and elegance of the subject have always been overlooked by the students. However, exploring the Fibonacci sequence can change this perspective. This fascinating topic uncovers hidden patterns within our world and the universe, particularly through its compelling connection with the Golden Ratio.

The Fibonacci sequence is defined as a sequence with two initial terms of 1. And to find the next term, simply add the two preceding terms. Thus, the sequence is as follows:

1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34, 55, 89, 144, 233, and so on.

The story of the Fibonacci sequence began with its appearance in the book of Leonardo of Pisa, *Liber Abaci*, as a rabbit problem, which was published in 1202. The book was used to introduce and popularize the Hindu-Arabic numeral system, which we use today. In one section of the book, Leonardo of Pisa introduced this rabbit problem:

"A man put a male-female pair of newly born rabbits in a field. Rabbits take a month to mature before mating. One month after mating, females give birth to one male-female pair and then mate again. No rabbits die. How many rabbit pairs are there after one year?" (Translation from Math Libretxts)

Solving the problem, there will be 233 pairs of rabbits after one year. Following the conditions presented in the problem, a sequence will be formed. This sequence is what we called as the Fibonacci sequence. So, the famous Fibonacci sequence is simply a solution to the rabbit problem. And the interesting fact is that the rabbit problem is not actually the highlight of that book; it is just an exercise.

Given its non-significance in the book, some mathematicians became fascinated with the rabbit problem. One of them was Édouard Lucas, a French mathematician, who officially named the rabbit problem as the Fibonacci sequence in 1877 (Ghose, 2024). But why is it called Fibonacci sequence, not Pisa sequence or Leonardo sequence? Historians in the 19th century came up with this nickname for him, Fibonacci, to distinguish him from other Leonardo during his time (Ghose, 2024). The name Fibonacci was derived from the Latin term "filius," which means "son," and the name Bonacci, which translates to "son of Bonacci." This is because his father's name was Guglielmo Bonacci.

Interestingly, if we work closely with the Fibonacci numbers, we can discover something fascinating. As cited by Brahier (2019), mathematician Johannes Kepler discovered the connection between the Fibonacci sequence and the golden ratio. He discovered that the ratio of two consecutive Fibonacci numbers created a new sequence, and it approaches the mysterious Divine Proportion, or commonly known as the golden ratio, which is approximately equal to 1.618. Presented below are the Fibonacci sequence and the ratio of consecutive Fibonacci numbers:

Fibonacci Sequence	Ratio of Consecutive Fibonacci Numbers
1	-
1	1
2	2
3	1.5
5	1.6666666667
8	1.6
13	1.625
21	1.61538461538
34	1.61904761905
55	1.61764705882
89	1.61818181818
144	1.61797752809
233	1.61805555556
377	1.61802575107
610	1.6180371353
987	1.6180327869
1597	1.6180344478
2584	1.6180338134
...	

Based on the table, we can observe that as the Fibonacci numbers increase, their ratio approaches the golden ratio. This observation leads us to an interesting insight. If we focus on the ratios and do some manipulations, we can see another perspective that reveals the meaningful connection between the Fibonacci numbers and the golden ratio.

Let's begin with the first ratio, which is $\frac{1}{1}$, and that gives us 1. Expressed as an equation, we have $\frac{1}{1} = 1$. The next ratio is $\frac{2}{1}$, and we are going to rewrite this using only the number 1 for the purpose of derivation. Thus, we have $\frac{1+1}{1}$, and let's rewrite it as:

$$\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{1} = 1 + \frac{1}{1}$$

Now, let's proceed to the next ratio, which is $\frac{3}{2}$. Like the previous ratios, let's rewrite this using only the number 1. So, we have $\frac{2+1}{2} = \frac{2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}$. Since on the previous ratio, we have shown that $2 = 1 + \frac{1}{1}$. Therefore, by substituting 2 with $1 + \frac{1}{1}$, we have:

$$\frac{3}{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{1}}$$

To continue, the next ratio is $\frac{5}{3}$. So, doing what we have been doing on the previous ratios, we have $\frac{3+2}{3} = \frac{3}{3} + \frac{2}{3} = 1 + \frac{2}{3}$. Now, the question that will arise here is that, how we can change $\frac{2}{3}$ to become a complex fraction with only ones. Previously, we have defined that $\frac{3}{2} = 1 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1}}$.

We know that $\frac{2}{3} = \frac{1}{\frac{3}{2}}$. Using this fact, we can show that $\frac{5}{3} = 1 + \frac{2}{3} = 1 + \frac{1}{\frac{3}{2}}$. Substituting $\frac{3}{2}$ by $1 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1}}$, we have,

$$\frac{5}{3} = 1 + \frac{2}{3} = 1 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1}}}$$

Moving on to the next ratio, we have $\frac{8}{5}$. Rewriting this, we have $\frac{8}{5} = \frac{5+3}{5} = \frac{5}{5} + \frac{3}{5} = 1 + \frac{3}{5}$. Using the fact that $\frac{3}{5} = \frac{1}{\frac{5}{3}}$, we have

$$\frac{8}{5} = 1 + \frac{3}{5} = 1 + \frac{1}{\frac{5}{3}} = 1 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1}}}}$$

Continuing this process, we will result in a continued fraction with only ones. Now, let's define the golden ratio as equal to this continued fraction, which continues infinitely. So, we have

$$\phi = 1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{\dots}}}}$$

Using the Fibonacci numbers, we can rewrite the golden ratio using an infinite continued fraction where the pattern repeats indefinitely. Now, solving for the value of ϕ , we can simplify the equation above by replacing the denominator on the right-hand side with ϕ , since they are equal as shown in the original equation. Therefore, the resulting equation will be,

$$\phi = 1 + \frac{1}{\phi}$$

Now, let's solve for the value of ϕ using the method of completing the square.

Step 1	$\phi = 1 + \frac{1}{\phi}$ $\phi^2 = \phi + 1$	Multiply both sides by ϕ to eliminate the denominator.
Step 2	$\phi^2 - \phi = 1$	Subtract ϕ from both sides.
Step 3	$\phi^2 - \phi + \frac{1}{4} = 1 + \frac{1}{4}$ $\phi^2 - \phi + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{5}{4}$	Add $\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{4}$ to both sides to complete the square.

Step 4	$\left(\phi - \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{5}{4}$	Rewrite the left side as a perfect square.
Step 5	$\phi - \frac{1}{2} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2}$	Take the square root of both sides.
Step 6	$\phi = \frac{1}{2} \pm \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2}$ $\phi = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2}$	Add $\frac{1}{2}$ to both sides to solve for ϕ .
Step 7	$\phi = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618 \dots$	The golden ratio is the positive solution.

Therefore, the values of ϕ are $\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ and $\frac{1-\sqrt{5}}{2}$. By taking the positive result, we obtain $\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.61803398875 \dots$ This is now the value of the golden ratio. It is an irrational number, as its decimal part continues indefinitely without any discernible pattern.

It is truly mind-blowing how a simple exercise involving rabbits could lead us to the Divine proportion, the golden ratio. This shows the true elegance of mathematics: from one simple concept and through manipulation, it unveils connections to other mathematical truths. While many students find these abstract concepts difficult to comprehend, studying and appreciating them allows us to uncover the hidden patterns carved in the world we live in. With the vast influence of the golden ratio, we have to ask: is this all just a coincidence? Perhaps the Fibonacci sequence was never a solution to the rabbit problem, but a purposeful sequence left for us to discover, suggesting a higher being who intended for us to fathom the true beauty of the universe through mathematics.

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